

Expectations and experience: IT jobs in offshore software development and commercial banks in Sri Lanka

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Abstract:

The purpose of this paper is to investigate job expectations, experience, and met expectations of IT professionals in offshore software development and commercial banks in Sri Lanka.

For the study, quantitative research methodology was used and data were collected from 342 and 208 IT professionals engaged full-time in offshore software development and commercial banks, respectively, in Sri Lanka. Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, paired sample t-test, independent sample t-test, and binary logistic regression were used appropriately for data analysis.

The findings of the study led to identify job expectations, experience, and met expectations of IT professionals that discriminate between offshore software development and commercial banks.

The literature provides evidence that job expectations of IT professionals in offshore software development are different from their counterparts in other comparable occupations. Therefore, the paper argues that sectoral differences in job expectations, experience, and met expectations of IT professionals are worthy of empirical investigation. Although the growth of services sector has resulted in extensive employment opportunities for IT professionals in South Asia, the details on their job expectations and whether their expectations vary by the business sector remain obscure.

Keywords: Commercial banks, Offshore software development, Job expectations, Met expectations, Sri Lanka, Banks, Information technology

Research paper

Introduction

Organisations increasingly resort to individuals with specialized expertise for enhanced corporate performance and competitiveness. During past decades employment landscape has changed and new expert occupational groups have emerged in fields such as information technology (IT) and incumbents of these new occupations are identified as knowledge workers. In Sri Lanka, like other countries, IT professionals (ITPs) could be identified as one of the vital resources of the country in its quest to become a technologically advanced nation.

The literature suggests, on the one hand, that although the need for IT talent is expanding, corresponding growth in the supply of IT talent is not up to expectation (Scholarios and Marks, 2004; SLICTA 2007). On the other hand, ITPs have higher levels of achievement motivation than professionals in many other comparable occupations (Lounsbury et al., 2007). ITPs who find their expectations are unmet in current workplaces may find alternative employment opportunities plentiful (Scholarios and Marks, 2004). Hence, they enjoy considerable labour market power, which has encouraged their mobility across organisations instead of promoting loyalty to a single organisation. In this context, retention as well as the optimization of job performance have become areas of increasing concern.

When looking for strategies to retain and optimize job performance of ITPs, first, the literature provides evidence that individuals bring to the employment situation their own expectations of what the job will be like (Porter and Steers, 1973). After entering into the organisation, they compare their initial expectations with their actual job experience; job expectations should be substantially met for them to feel worthwhile and remain with the organisation (Porter and Steers, 1973). Previous studies suggest that ITPs report higher levels of job expectations than others in comparable occupations; yet, they report lower levels of satisfaction than those in comparable occupations (Couger, 1990; Igbaria and Wormley, 1992). Therefore, met expectations of ITPs offer an understanding of how their perception towards the job has evolved and causes for that perception. Such an

understanding is useful in determining strategies to address job expectations, experience, and thereby met expectations.

Second, there is a need to explore career systems operating in different business sectors in different parts of the world to broaden our understanding on region specific and sector specific differences (Ballou and Huguenard, 2008; Budhwar and Debrah, 2009). However, our review of literature suggests that all most all available empirical research on job expectations of ITPs were conducted in the West some time ago (e.g. Couger, 1990, Igbaria and Wormley, 1992). Although the growth of services sector has resulted in extensive employment opportunities for ITPs in the South Asia during the past decades our review of literature suggests a paucity of direct empirical data on their job expectations.

Third, although the literature suggests that ITPs in different business sectors may have different job expectations (Ballou and Huguenard, 2008), very little is known about ITPs' job expectations, experience and met expectations across different business sectors. For the study, ITPs attached full-time to two different business sectors were selected, i.e., offshore software development (OSD) and commercial banks (CBs) in Sri Lanka. OSD emerged in Sri Lanka due to a growing tendency of Western countries to offshore outsource various IT work to other countries during the late 1990s. Compared to OSD sector, commercial banking is a traditional sector that existed in Sri Lanka since 1881. Yet, details on job expectations of ITPs in the South Asia (Sri Lanka in particular) and whether their expectations vary by the business sector remain obscure. In this context, the study investigated job expectations, experience, and met expectations of ITPs in OSD and CBs in Sri Lanka.

Literature review and hypotheses

Job characteristics and met expectations

Job design and preferred job characteristics. The design of a job describes the structure, content, and configuration of a person's work tasks, roles and work environment (Erez, 2010). As a core human resource (HR) activity job design refers to "deciding on the actual

job structure - that is, identifying the relevant tasks and allocating them across employees in a way that allows the organization to reap benefits from specialization, as well as bundling job tasks to take into account possible synergies between tasks” (Foss et al., 2009, p. 873). Job design has an immediate influence on an individual’s perception as facilitating or inhibiting opportunities for being successful and for experiencing self-worth and well-being (Erez, 2010, p. 389).

The early scholarly work on job design focused on bringing greater control and efficiency to the workplace by designing work systems with standardized operations and highly simplified work (Taylor, 1911). Herzberg (1976) provided a valuable point of departure by claiming that jobs should be designed and managed to foster responsibility, achievement, growth, recognition, and advancement. The work of Hackman and Oldham (1976) concentrated on identifying the characteristics of jobs that foster a state of internal work motivation to perform jobs. Hackman and Oldham (1976) identified skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and job-based feedback as the core characteristics of jobs. Recently, researchers have extended Hackman and Oldham’s (1976) job characteristics theory with constructs such as felt responsibility for constructive change, perceived social impact, trust by others and self, motivation to make a prosocial difference, information processing, job complexity, specialization, problem solving, physical demands, and social support (refer to Foss et al., 2009).

The dimensionality of job and work design are important in making decisions by individuals as well as organizations. For instance, Osterman (2010) identifies job characteristics as a list of attributes clustered together in logical and self-reinforcing ways (e.g., rewards), which employees consider in assessing the quality of a job and employers consider in making HR decisions. Further, Oldham and Hackman (2010, p. 471) suggest that employees often compare the characteristics of their own jobs with those of others in their work units - and that they have negative reactions when they perceive their jobs to be relatively lower in quality. Furthermore, Hall and Las Heras (2010) argue that individuals make decisions at different points in their careers by prioritizing certain job characteristics

over others so that those job characteristics will be instrumental in achieving career success. In this regard, Hall and Las Heras (2010, p.451) argue that job characteristics such as task significance and task identity, which represent the meaning of genuine work, may correlate more strongly with subjective success than with objective success while factors such as feedback and autonomy, which are linked with an individual's work efficiency, may correlate more strongly with objective success than subjective success (Hall and Las Heras, 2010).

However, the literature suggests that current theoretical models and empirical studies on the dimensionality of job and work design have yet to integrate the changing contexts within which work is performed (Grant et al., 2010; Humphrey et al., 2007; Oldham and Hackman, 2010; Parker et al., 2001; Sparrow, 2000; Steers et al., 2004). According to Oldham and Hackman (2010), although specific, well-defined jobs perform by individuals who work mostly independently of one another in bounded, stand-alone organizations continue to exist in the contemporary world of work, fundamental changes have occurred in the relationships among people, the work they do, and the organizations for which they do it. For instance, life-time employment has become far from the norm and layoffs have increasingly become strategies for restructuring (Osterman, 2010). Internal labour markets have become flatter implying that promotions are difficult to obtain and climbing up the hierarchy will be slower (Osterman, 2010) and also implying that employees now move between organizations much more often than earlier (Parker et al., 2001). Further, growth in contingent work, more individualized career paths, altered psychological contracts between employers and employees, and the changing composition of the workforce and generational differences are some other new issues that assumed considerable importance in the contemporary world of work (Grant et al., 2010; Hall and Las Heras, 2010; Oldham and Hackman, 2010). Furthermore, developments in information and communications technology have important implications for the way in which work is conducted (e.g., geographic virtuality, temporal virtuality, teleworking, globally distributed virtual teams) (Grant et al., 2010; Oldham and Hackman, 2010; Parker et al., 2001). In addition, there is an increasing prominence of work that is performed by teams rather than individuals. Employees may work

in temporary teams, where membership shifts as work requirements change or they may serve on a project team, where other members come from different organizations (Oldham and Hackman, 2010). In this regard, the literature suggests the importance of studying offshore outsourcing since many Western jobs have been transported to overseas to take advantages of lower costs and broader talent pools in developing countries (Grant et al., 2010). For instance, Grant et al. (2010) stress the importance of knowing whether these economies use new job design ideas because of their lack of resources. One of the sectors investigated in the present study is offshore software development, which is recognized to use project-based globally distributed team structures.

Institutional setting and HR practices in IT and banking sectors. Although some studies reported that employment practices in developing countries tend to be less institutionalized, less structured, and less impactful (Yeung et al., 2008), research findings in the context of Sri Lanka do not support such claims (Akuratiyagamage, 2006; Dharmasiri, 2009; Mamman et al., 2006; Wickramasinghe, 2006). The research studies of Akuratiyagamage (2006), Dharmasiri (2009), Mamman et al. (2006), and Wickramasinghe (2006) provide evidence that firms have adopted relatively sophisticated HR systems that reflect global best practices. For instance, in a study that investigated the strategic orientation of HR managers in commercial banks, Dharmasiri (2009) found that commercial banks in Sri Lanka have satisfactory levels of strategic orientation. Further, Akuratiyagamage (2006) and Mamman et al. (2006) did not find significant differences across firms of different ownership (local and MNCs) for HR practices, importance given to the HR function in organisational strategy and HR managers' contribution to organisational strategy. Further, when considering the research studies conducted in the context of India, Budhwar et al. (2006) and Stumpf et al. (2010) found that BPOs (including IT and software services) have adopted sophisticated HR practices. For instance, Budhwar et al. (2006) found that the work organisation of Indian BPOs is highly structured, tightly controlled, bureaucratic, formalized, and monitored; the employment practices of recruitment, training,

compensation, and performance appraisal are formal and structured and appear to be somewhat similar to their Western counterparts. According to Mamman et al. (2006), the lack of significant differences between local firms and MNCs in Sri Lanka imply that globalization is contributing to the diffusion and convergence of management practices, and they suggested that drivers of globalization such as non-governmental organisations, efficient communication systems, IT, and international and professional institutions might have played some roles in the transfer of management practices and philosophies.

Therefore, the literature reviewed above on previous studies conducted in the context of Sri Lanka (and also in India) suggests that irrespective of the business sector, i.e., manufacturing or services (such as banking and BPOs, including IT and software services), firms have adopted relatively sophisticated employment systems that reflect global best practices. In this context, the literature is reviewed below on the nature of HR practices used in IT and banking sectors to better understand IT jobs experienced by ITPs.

HR practices in IT sector. In the Sri Lankan context, salaries enjoyed by ITPs were identified as the best of all industries (SLICTA, 2007). Firms identified a good compensation plan, good work environment, challenging job, clear career path and training as the most important attributes that help them retain ITPs irrespective of their work experience. Further, firms identified on-the-job training as the most preferred method of skill development followed by self-study (SLICTA, 2007). In this regard, Akuratiyagamage (2006) found that effective skill development processes were in place in Sri Lanka with sufficient integration with organisational strategy, job analysis, succession planning, and performance appraisal.

IT firms are likely to standardize jobs to facilitate rapid replacement considering ITPs as “short-timers”; acquire ITPs with required capabilities from external labour market, focus on their short-term job performance with short-term productivity targets, and pay them market-based rewards maintaining internal equity (Wickramasinghe and Mahahettige, 2011; Sanjeevani, 2009). Further, opportunities available for promotion are few and far between, and premium on industry experience is very high in compensation decisions (Wickramasinghe and Mahahettige, 2011). Specific experience in a particular job position

comes out as the first preference of IT firms across almost all job categories among factors considered during recruitment (SLICTA, 2007) and firms' preference for job specific experience gives ITPs a feeling that their experience is rewarded (Wickramasinghe, 2009). In this regard, Annual labour turnover rate of IT workforce was 13%; 72% of the IT workforce have less than five years of total work experience (SLICTA, 2007). Wickramasinghe (2009) found that work experience is a significant factor in predicting job satisfaction of ITPs in IT offshoring firms, where ITPs with a longer tenure in their present workplace were less satisfied with their jobs, feel a loss of interest in IT jobs in IT offshoring firms and intend to leave their present workplace. In this regard, Boh et al. (2001) describe IT profession as boundaryless because of relatively high inter-organisational mobility although much of this mobility may take place within the boundaries of IT occupations. Yet, in the context of India, Budhwar et al. (2006) suggest that many human issues in the Indian BPOs (including IT and software services) could be addressed by developing appropriate career-related policies.

With regard to work environment, past studies suggest that working time is an important characteristic of OSD in Sri Lanka, where increased levels of voluntary working time extensions to fulfil daily workloads could decrease ITPs' job satisfaction, which subsequently could increase their turnover intention (Wickramasinghe, 2010). In this regard, Perlow (2001) argues that long hours are not inherent in the work of OSD; alterations in the nature of management and different ideas about how to organize work could develop different OSD work settings although the work itself is the same.

Several previous studies conducted in India provide evidence that ITPs experience job stress and suggested that firms could overcome this problem by providing workplace flexibility (Budhwar et al. 2006). In this regard, Wickramasinghe and Jayabandu (2007) provide evidence that OSD firms in Sri Lanka have introduced work schedule flexibility, and as a consequence, ITPs experience less restriction at work. Wickramasinghe (2012) also provides evidence that supervisor support moderates the relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress of ITPs attached to OSD. However, Wickramasinghe and

Jayabandu (2007) suggested that although work schedule flexibility could be used as a strategy in attracting prospective ITPs, it would not be effective in retaining them.

Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera (2010) found that ITPs in OSD sector are not experiencing job content plateau and it could be due to the use of project based work environment that facilitates lateral and cross-functional moves meeting both organisation's needs for flexibility and individual's need for broad-based career experience. Further, Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera (2010) found that supervisory career support significantly predicts ITPs' career satisfaction while hierarchical plateau and job content plateau do not significantly predict their career satisfaction.

HR practices in banking sector. Very limited number of studies have investigated HR practices specific to banking sector in Sri Lanka as well as in the global context (e.g. Akuratiyagamage and Opatha, 2004; Kumudha and Abraham, 2008; Kaur and Sandhu, 2010; Stumpf et al., 2010). With regard to job characteristics experience by managers attached to commercial banks, Akuratiyagamage and Opatha (2004) investigated causes of grievances of managers in commercial banks in Sri Lanka, and found that job attributes of lack of authority, nature of duties, and nature of targets gave them higher levels of grievances than other job attributes such as interpersonal relations and physical working conditions.

In the context of banking sector in India, Kaur and Sandhu (2010) found that banking sector employees' organisational commitment vary by their tenure, where employees with a longer tenure (exceeding 10 years) were significantly more committed than those with less than 10 years of tenure. Further, Kumudha and Abraham (2008) found that career management programmes contribute to banking sector employees' feeling of career satisfaction in India. Further, in a comparative study of three business sectors in India, namely services sector (included financial service), IT sector, and manufacturing sector, Stumpf et al. (2010) found that HR practices were perceived to be the most effective among services firms, the least so among IT firms, with manufacturing firms falling in the middle.

Further, Stumpf et al. (2010) found a strong relationship between performance management and individual career success in services sector than in manufacturing or IT sectors.

Expectations, experience, and met expectations. The literature suggests that employees form their own unique expectations of what the job will be like before entering a new job and bring those to the employment situation (Porter and Steers, 1973; Wanous et al., 1992). In general, employees have expectations about job attributes such as content, rewards, career opportunities and professional relationships, and employees place high salience on the attainment of these expectations (Wanous et al., 1992). As a consequence, after entering the organisation, they compare their initial expectations when taking the job with their job experience such as the rate of promotion and salary increases. The discrepancy between what employees really encountered and what they expected to encounter is conceptualized as met expectations. The term met expectation is, therefore, referred to explain “the discrepancy between what a person encounters on his (or her) job in the way of positive and negative experiences and what he (or she) expected to encounter” (Porter and Steers, 1973, p. 152).

Porter and Steers (1973) suggest that job expectations must be substantially met for an employee to feel worthwhile and remain with the organisation. The literature further suggests that it is the comparison between expectations and experience that influence employees' attitudes and behaviour, and it is not either one alone that influences one's attitudes and behaviour (Caligiuri et al., 2001; Irving and Montes, 2009). In this regard, Irving and Montes (2009, p. 445) suggest that “... delivered inducements contributed much more to the prediction of employee satisfaction than did expected inducements. This implies that although expectations are used as a comparison standard against which to evaluate subsequent experiences, it is the delivered inducements that will largely determine employee reactions”.

The findings of previous studies suggest that if the discrepancy between expectations and reality is reduced, employees' level of job satisfaction (Major et al., 1995),

adjustment to work environment (e.g. Caligiuri et al., 2001), psychological contract (Caligiuri et al., 2001), and organisational commitment (Major et al., 1995) will increase while intention to leave (Porter and Steers, 1973) will decrease. In this regard, Chandraiah et al. (2003) found that role expectation conflict is one of the main stressors in the early career group (25–35 years) in India. Therefore, the extent to which employees' job expectations are met has important consequences to organizations (such as employee turnover and job satisfaction).

Expectations, experience, and met expectations of ITPs. With regard to the specific literature on ITPs, previous studies suggest that job expectations, experience and, as a consequence, met expectations are particularly important for ITPs (Couger, 1990; Igbaria and Wormley, 1992). For instance, Couger (1990) suggests that due to the relative shortage of ITPs in the labour market they tend to have higher expectations about their jobs than other employee groups.

With regard to differences in ITPs' job expectations by business sector, previous studies suggested that ITPs who choose to work at consulting firms may be different from ITPs who choose to work at non-consulting firms (Ballou and Huguenard, 2008; Smits et al., 1993). For instance, it was found that jobs in consulting firms provide ITPs with variety of tasks, creativity, challenge, permit a reasonable amount of autonomy, and a sense of accomplishment (Smits et al., 1993) and, therefore, ITPs who work for consulting firms are more satisfied with their choice of careers (Ballou and Huguenard, 2008). Overall, these studies imply that job attributes searched by ITPs attached to different business sectors, which employ ITPs with almost the same credentials, could be different. Although the literature suggests that the proposition of met expectation can be used to explain organizational factors that affect attitudes or behaviour of employees (Irving and Montes, 2009), to date, no empirical studies have been conducted to investigate ITPs' expectations of what the job and job environment will be like before entering a new job and whether their expectations vary by the business sector.

Propositions

The literature reviewed above on *job design and preferred job characteristics* suggests that employees make important career decisions based on the dimensionality of job and work design (such as Hall and Las Heras, 2010; Humphrey et al., 2007; Oldham and Hackman, 2010; Osterman, 2010). That is, employees expect jobs to foster certain attributes such as responsibility, autonomy, job complexity, achievement, job-based feedback, growth, recognition, advancement, and social support for them to cultivate a state of internal work motivation to perform jobs. Further, employees compare the characteristics of their own jobs with those of others, and as a consequence they may have negative reactions if they perceive their jobs to be relatively lower in quality (Oldham and Hackman, 2010). To understand this situation further, the literature on *expectations, experience, and met expectations* is useful. According to the proposition of met expectation, employees bring sets of expectations to their employment situation; they place high salience on the attainment of these expectations; their attitudes and behaviours are outcomes of a process in which they compare their level of expectations with their perceived realities (Caligiuri et al., 2001; Irving and Montes, 2009; Wanous et al., 1992). Hence, based on the job characteristics employees experience and their expectations, they make decisions at different points in their careers by prioritizing certain job characteristics over others.

When making a connection between *job characteristics* experienced by ITPs in OSD and *job expectations* of ITPs in OSD, the literature reviewed above (such as Wickramasinghe, 2009; Wickramasinghe and Mahahettige, 2011; Sanjeewani, 2009; SLICTA, 2007) suggests that ITPs attached to OSD experience standardize jobs that allow rapid replacement; employers consider them as short-times and emphasize short-term job performance with short-term productivity targets, organisation sponsored training aimed at immediate skill applications, and experience limited promotional opportunities. Further, ITPs with a longer tenure in their present workplace were less satisfied with their jobs and their annual labour turnover is very high (Wickramasinghe, 2009; SLICTA, 2007). The findings of Scholarios and Marks (2004) and Lounsbury et al. (2007) in the context of the West also

suggests that ITPs have higher levels of expectations than professionals in many other comparable occupations and ITPs whose job expectations are unmet by their present workplace are likely to get those fulfilled from elsewhere (Couger, 1990; Igbaria and Wormley, 1992; Scholarios and Marks, 2004). Overall, these findings suggest that ITPs in OSD may have high job expectations and as a consequence, they may not have met their expectations. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H1: Job expectations of ITPs in OSD will be higher than their job experience

H2: Job expectations of ITPs in OSD will be higher than their met expectations

When making a connection between *job characteristics* experienced by ITPs in CBs and *job expectations* of ITPs in CBs, the literature reviewed above suggests that employees in CBs experience higher levels of grievances in relation to job characteristics such as authority and the nature of job tasks (Akuratiyagamage and Opatha, 2004). Such findings imply that ITPs attached to CBs may have higher levels of expectations for their preferred job characteristics, and as a consequence, may not have met their expectations. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H3: Job expectations of ITPs in CBs will be higher than their job experience

H4: Job expectations of ITPs in CBs will be higher than their met expectations

The literature also suggests that there are differences in HR practices and *job characteristics* experienced by employees attached to *different business sectors* (e.g. Stumpf et al., 2010). For instance, Stumpf et al. (2010) found that HR practices in financial services are much better than that of IT firms. And also, there is a strong relationship between performance management and individual career success in the services sector than in the IT sector (Stumpf et al., 2010). In the Sri Lankan context, ITPs are employed by three employer groups, namely, IT sector (also known as IT suppliers, such as OSD), non-IT Sector (also known as ICT users, such as commercial banking) and the Government (SLICTA, 2007). Of approximately a 30,000 total IT workforce in the country, IT sector has

approximately a 13,000 members, and the majority of them are employed in firms that supply products and services to offshore client firms. Non-IT sector has approximately a 14,000 members while the Government sector has approximately a 2000 members. With regard to HR practices used to manage employees attached to IT and non-IT sectors, SLICTA (2007) suggests that there is a difference between IT and non-IT sector employers' perception of average firm tenure expected from new recruits from the day they start work. IT sector expected new recruits, in almost every job category, to stay for at least two years from the day they start while non-IT sector expected them to stay for at least three years from the day they start (SLICTA, 2007). This implies that firms do not expect long-term commitment from their ITPs, and as a consequence, there may be differences in the HR practices used to manage ITPs by the two sectors.

When making a connection between *job characteristics and job expectations* of ITPs in *different business sectors*, the literature reviewed above suggests that job attributes searched by ITPs attached to various business sectors could be different (such as Ballou and Huguenard, 2008; Smits et al., 1993). In the Sri Lankan context, the literature reveals that annual labour turnover rate was 16%, 8%, and 2% in the IT sector, non-IT sector, the Government sector, respectively (SLICTA, 2007). Further, the majority of ITPs with work experience of five years or more were employed in the non-IT sector (SLICTA, 2007). This implies that ITPs attached to non-IT sector may have met their expectations to a considerable extent than ITPs attached to IT sector.

Hence, based on the literature reviewed above on HR practices and job characteristics, it is possible to argue that ITPs attached to CBs may experience better job conditions than OSD. Further, previous studies identified IT offshoring sector as a product of economic globalisation and the context of this sector itself may shape expectations of ITPs attached to this sector (Wickramasinghe, 2009). Furthermore, salaries enjoyed by ITPs can be identified as the best of all industries in Sri Lanka (SLICTA, 2007). This implies that ITPs with higher expectations are more attracted to this sector. Hence, based on such literature reviewed above, it is possible to argue that ITPs' expectations, experience, and met

expectations will be different by the business sector, where ITPs attached CBs may have met their expectations to a considerable degree than ITPs attached to OSD. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H5: Job expectations of ITPs in OSD will be higher than job expectations of ITPs in CBs

H6: Job experience of ITPs in OSD will be lower than job experience of ITPs in CBs

H7: Met expectations of ITPs in OSD will be lower than met expectations of ITPs in CBs

Methodology

Measures

Job expectations, experience and met expectations. We were unable to find empirical studies with ready to use questionnaire items addressing job expectations, experience and met expectations appropriate for our study. However, several previous studies guided us in developing questionnaire items for remuneration (such as Irving and Montes, 2009; Taris et al., 2005), skill development (such as Irving and Montes, 2009), support from others (such as Irving and Montes, 2009), advancement opportunity (such as Taris et al., 2005), job security (such as Taris et al., 2005), control over work (such as Hackman and Oldham, 1976; Hall and Las Heras, 2010; Oldham and Hackman, 2010; Taris et al., 2005), and job challenges (such as Hackman and Oldham, 1976; Hall and Las Heras, 2010; Oldham and Hackman, 2010; Taris et al., 2005). Based on such literature reviewed and information gathered during our preliminary investigations on ITPs in Sri Lanka, 24-item scale was developed to address ITPs' expectations, experience and met expectations.

When evaluating expectations, respondents rated the extent to which they expected their employer to provide them with each of 24 attributes on a five-point scale ranging from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important) (refer to Appendix 1).

When evaluating job experience, respondents rated the extent to which they received each of these same 24 attributes on a five-point scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) (refer to Appendix 2).

When evaluating met expectations, methodologies followed by previous research were reviewed thoroughly (such as Igbaria and Wormley, 1992; Irving and Montes, 2009). For this study, the above mentioned 24 items were used as a direct measure to assess met expectations. That is, respondents indicated whether their experience of each of these same 24 attributes were much more (5), somewhat more, about the same, somewhat less, or much less than what they had expected (1) when they began employment with the present firm on the five-point scale (refer to Appendix 3). This procedure was earlier used by Igbaria and Wormley (1992) in the context of ITPs.

Factor analysis was conducted for expectations, experience and met expectations separately. 21 items loaded into six factors. These six factors were labelled as “Work-life balance”, “Job security, remuneration and advancement opportunity”, “Identification with the organisation”, “Control over work”, “Perceptibility of expertise”, and “Job challenges”. Three items failed to load satisfactorily during the factor analysis. These items were opportunity to make friends, feeling of self-fulfilment, and permits regular in time and place of work. The items used and results of factor analyses are shown in Appendix 1, 2, and 3.

Controls. Hierarchical plateau, job content plateau, supervisor support, and individual demographic characteristics were controlled. The items used and results of factor analyses relating to hierarchical plateau, job content plateau and supervisor support are shown in Appendix 4. Hierarchical plateau was measured using a) the number of years an individual is serving in the current position, and b) the six-item scale developed by Milliman (1992), which has been widely used in previous studies (such as Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel, 2009). The items were on a five-point scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) where higher scores indicated higher levels of hierarchical plateauing.

Perceived job content plateau was measured using the six-item scale developed by Milliman (1992), which has been widely used in previous studies (such as Armstrong-Stassen and Ursel, 2009). The items were on a five-point scale ranging from 1 (strongly

disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) where higher scores indicated higher levels of job content plateauing.

Perceived supervisor support was measured using three items drawn from Eisenberger et al.'s (1986) scale. Following Eisenberger et al. (2002), we also replaced the term "organisation" with "supervisor".

Of the demographic characteristics, gender (female – 0, male - 1), marital status (single - 0, married - 1), the highest level of education (Diploma - 0, Degree - 1), total employees in the present workplace (below 250 - 0, more than 250 – 1), the number of employees in the unit (below 20 – 0, more than 20 – 1) were binary coded. Age, position tenure, and firm tenure were measured in years.

Sample

An IT professional is defined as a person engaged full-time in producing IT related output as his or her primary job function (SLICTA, 2007, p. 7). For this study, OSD is selected to represent IT sector while commercial banking is selected to represent non-IT sector. There were 20 CBs and approximately 100 OSDs operating in the country. A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection and participants' responses were anonymous. Of the 500 survey questionnaires distributed among a randomly selected ITPs attached to OSD, 342 usable responses resulted in a 68% response rate; of the 250 survey questionnaires distributed among a randomly selected ITPs attached to CBs, 208 usable responses resulted in a 83% response rate. The demographics of the respondents are shown in Table 1. Respondents' previous work experience is summarized in Table 2.

Take in Table 1

Take in Table 2

Methods of data collection and data analysis

Considering the literacy of the respondents, the survey questionnaire was in the English language. It was pre-tested with a random sample that fitted with the intended samples of the study prior to distribution. Multiple items were used to measure a particular variable; respondents came from random samples of considerable size representing the two sectors. To overcome positive response bias, factor analysis was used following the recommended procedure by Hair et al. (2006). Procedural and statistical measures were taken to reduce common method bias following the recommended procedure by Podsakoff et al. (2003).

Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, paired sample t-test, independent sample t-test, and binary logistic regression were used appropriately for the data analysis. For the logistic regression, OSD is coded as “0” and commercial banking is coded as “1”.

Results and discussion

Mean values and standard deviations for the variables are shown in Appendix 1 to 4, Table 1, and Table 3. Correlations between the variables were analyzed; we have not detected high correlations suggesting multicollinearity in our analysis (refer to Hair et al., 2006) (results are not shown in a table).

Job expectations, experience, and met expectations of ITPs in OSD

It is apparent from Table 3 that job expectations are significantly higher than experience for all attributes except for perceptibility of expertise. Therefore, H1 is partially supported. Further, job expectations are significantly higher than met expectations for all attributes. Therefore, H2 is supported.

Take in Table 3

Job expectations, experience, and met expectations of ITPs in CBs

It is apparent from Table 3 that job expectations are significantly higher than experience for all attributes except for perceptibility of expertise. Therefore, H3 is partially supported.

Further, job expectations are significantly higher than met expectations for all attributes.

Therefore, H4 is supported.

Comparison across OSD and CBs

It is apparent that five attributes of job expectations are significantly higher for ITPs in CBs than ITPs in OSD except for job challenges (refer to Table 3 for mean values). However, the difference is not significant for job challenges by sector (refer Table 4). Therefore, H5 is partially supported. According to the results of logistic regression, Nagelkerke R² of 0.829 suggests that 83% of the variance is explained by the covariates. *P* value of 0.698 of Hosmer and Lemeshow test suggests a good fit. The overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 92 (91.7%). It is evident from Table 5 that all the five attributes (except job challenges) represent important job expectations that discriminate between OSD and CBs. For instance, the odds of ITPs in CBs to perceive a higher level of “work-life balance” (as opposed to ITPs in OSD) are 21 (21.35) times as high.

Take in Table 4

Take in Table 5

It is apparent that job experiences of ITPs in CBs are significantly higher than ITPs in OSD for four attributes except for control over work and job challenges (refer to Table 3 for mean values). However, the difference is not significant for job challenges by sector (refer Table 4); mean values for control over work is significantly high for ITPs in OSD than ITPs in CBs (refer Table 3 and 4). Therefore, H6 is partially supported. According to the results of logistic regression, Nagelkerke R² of 0.802 suggests that 80% of the variance is explained

by the covariates. *P* value of 0.970 of Hosmer and Lemeshow test suggests a good fit. The overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 90 (90.0%). It is evident from Table 5 that all the five attributes (except job challenges) represent important job experience that discriminate between OSD and CBs. For instance, the odds of ITPs from CBs to perceive a higher level of “identification with the organisation” (as opposed to ITPs from OSD) are 22 (22.15) times as high. The odds of ITPs from OSD to perceive a higher level of “control over work” (as opposed to ITPs in CBs) are 1.2 (1.158) times as high.

It is apparent that met expectations of ITPs in CBs are significantly higher for all attributes than ITPs in OSD (refer Table 3 and 4). Therefore, H7 supported. According to the results of logistic regression, Nagelkerke R^2 of 0.764 suggests that 76% of the variance is explained by the covariates. *P* value of 0.737 of Hosmer and Lemeshow test suggests a good fit. The overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 89 (89.2%). It is evident from Table 5 that all the six attributes represent important met expectations that discriminate between OSD and CBs. For instance, the odds of ITPs from CBs to perceive a higher level of “control over work” (as opposed to ITPs in OSD) are ten (9.674) times as high.

Table 6 summarises the results of the hypotheses testing.

Take in Table 6

Conclusions and implications

The study investigated job expectations, experience, and met expectations of ITPs in OSD and CBs in Sri Lanka. Although it is very rare to find previous empirical studies that resemble the current study to make straight forward comparisons, in general, the findings of the current study support previous studies that identified employees seek control over work (e.g. Igbaria and Wormley, 1992); value and prefer a certain level of pay, security, promotions,

and financial incentives (e.g. Wanous et al., 1992) and seek challenging work assignments (Lounsbury et al., 2007).

Although previous research found that maintaining a balance between work and the rest of ITPs' life is important (Scholarios and Marks, 2004), the findings suggest that work-life balance is not very highly rated by ITPs attached to OSD. This situation could be explained by referring to the findings of SLICTA (2007) and Sturges and Guest (2004). SLICTA (2007) suggests that new entrants to the IT workforce in Sri Lanka are attracted mainly to the IT sector and more experienced ITPs seem to look outside the IT sector for new employment opportunities. According to Sturges and Guest (2004) young people may believe that the number of hours worked is associated with greater involvement in work while long hours appear to reflect the belief that one demonstrates commitment in terms of hours spent at work (at least during the early years of a career) in order to succeed in the corporate environment. This submission may also apply to ITPs attached to OSD. Yet, Chandraiah et al. (2003) found that unmet expectations lead to role expectation conflict in the early career group (25–35 years) in India.

Although we found that ITPs seek perceptibility of expertise and identification with the organisation, we have not come across previous studies conducted on knowledge workers that support our findings. Yet, the literature suggests that the high level of occupational identification among ITPs has encouraged them to identify themselves with the profession (Scholarios and Marks, 2004).

Although meeting of expectations may serve as a salient criterion in assessing career accomplishments as well as may help employees to function effectively and maintain a positive attitude, the results of paired sample t-test suggest that job expectations of ITPs in both sectors are unmet (refer to Table 3, H1 to H4) except perceptibility of expertise. In the case of perceptibility of expertise, it may be due to the fact that ITPs' initial expectations for perceptibility of expertise were closer to reality even though they held unrealistically high expectations for other job attributes. In this regard, Irving and Montes (2009) suggests that

more realistic expectations are more likely to be met on the job, thereby preventing employees from experiencing reality shock.

The study investigated differences in job expectations, experience and met expectations by sector. In terms of job expectations and experience, significant differences were found for five job attributes except for job challenges (refer to Table 4, H5 and H6). In terms of met expectations, significant differences were found for all the six job attributes (refer to Table 4, H7). Therefore, these represent important job attributes that discriminate between OSD and CBs. Therefore, the findings of our study support the claims made by Ballou and Huguenard (2008) and Smits et al. (1993) that ITPs' perceptions vary by the business sector. However, considerable future research is necessary to test our propositions and to replicate, extend, or disconfirm the results presented in this article.

The study makes several contributions to the literature as how to manage employees in different business sectors. This is a critical area of investigation for academics and researchers, with important practical implications for organisational leaders. With regard to the contribution of the study for the literature, there is surprisingly little previous empirical research that investigated job expectations, experience, and met expectations of ITPs and whether these vary by the business sector to which ITPs are attached to. Present study attempted to address this gap in the literature. Specifically, first, the literature suggests that Tayloristic scientific approach to job design created an environment that facilitates employees' efficiency and productivity while job characteristics theory had addressed some of the dimensions that were overlooked by the scientific perspective. Yet, more recent literature (such as Grant et al., 2010; Hall and Las Heras, 2010; Oldham and Hackman, 2010) emphasizes the importance of incorporating the features of contemporary work and work environment to better understand the expectations of present day employees. Hence, the findings of the current study are important for job design and many other HR practices such as careers and rewards.

Second, Deci and Ryan (2000) suggest that an individual's behaviour may no longer contingent on others' external rewards and punishments but rather on the feelings of self-

worth. The findings of the current study provide empirical evidence that ITPs value to be identified with the organization and value to be appreciated their expertise. Third, the literature identifies that job resources (such as job control and participation) enable an individual to manage job demands (Deci and Ryan, 2000). The findings of the current study provide empirical evidence that ITPs value discretion they have over timing and methods of work tasks in job control and influence they have over important issues in the work domain, which enables them to remove task obstacles and to fulfill their need for autonomy.

Fourth, the literature on careers suggests that careers are comprised of a series of job experiences and that careers are determined by job choices that people make over time (Hall and Las Heras, 2010). In this context, job characteristics that ITPs experience in the two sectors may influence how ITPs perceive their current job assignments and evaluate alternatives. Hence, the findings support the above argument by providing evidence that the dimensions and work design of IT jobs in OSDs and CBs are important determinants in making decisions by ITPs regarding their careers. Therefore, the findings of the study make a contribution to the literature by investigating dimensions and work design of IT jobs, job expectations, experience and met expectations of ITPs which may affect the future research on job design and careers. Therefore, we believe that the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

With regard to the contribution of the study for the practice, first, the findings imply that individuals' expectations not only include pay, promotion and job security, but also include other areas such as perceptibility of expertise and identification with the organisation. Second, the findings emphasize the need of providing accurate information about job attributes to job seekers and taking steps to deliver employees' realistic job expectations. In this regard, the literature suggests that successful organisational socialization may be inhibited if individuals' pre-entry job expectations are unmet once on the job (Irving and Montes, 2009). Therefore, the findings imply the importance of realistic job previews to generate more realistic expectations on the job, which will congruent with reality. However,

the provision of information from the part of the organisation alone is insufficient; individuals should be prepared to collect as much as possible information on job attributes of their prospective employers.

Third, the literature reviewed earlier suggests that employees place high salience on the attainment of their job expectations, and if their expectations are not substantially met, the propensity for them to withdraw from the organisation increases (Porter and Steers, 1973). In Sri Lanka, turnover rate of ITPs is considerably high (13%) (SLICTA, 2007). Hence, it is possible to argue that ITPs, whose job expectations are unmet by their present workplace are likely to get those fulfilled from elsewhere. Therefore, the findings suggest the importance of evaluating job expectations time to time to understand what ITPs are attempting to achieve and how they are attempting to achieve those. In doing so, the due attention should be given to job attributes searched by ITPs attached to different business sectors.

Fourth, the characteristics of samples and their job histories (Tables 1 and 2) suggest that a considerable number of ITPs move between different organisations across sectors in search for better conditions that meet their expectations. In this regard, it is possible to argue, on the one hand, that employees' salaries rise with firm tenure and therefore, mobility may have a negative impact on career outcomes, and on the other hand, mobility is unattractive to prospective employers as it signals a propensity to change jobs. However, these may not apply to ITPs in Sri Lanka. This may be because, the literature reviewed above on the Sri Lankan context suggests that firms expect ITPs to stay with a particular firm for a short time duration (in IT sector for about two years and in non-IT sector for about three years) from the day they start (SLICTA, 2007). Hence, on the one hand, firms may favour hiring ready-skilled employees at market rates rather than investing in training. On the other hand, mobility between jobs may facilitate regular updating of a range of specialized skills and knowledge of ITPs. As argued by Arthur et al. (2005) such mobility may facilitate to convert learning experience into career capital. Therefore, job histories of ITPs may suggest the potential of career capital in enhancing one's employability. This implies the importance

of examining job histories to understand the long-term effect of a series of jobs in different firms and their cumulative effect on the careers of ITPs.

Fifth, the literature reviewed earlier suggests that firms compete with each other to attract ITPs with almost similar credentials from the IT workforce of the country (SLICTA, 2007). Yet, as mentioned above, IT sector expects new recruits to stay with them for about two years whereas non-IT sector (such as commercial banking) expects new recruits to stay with them for about three years from the day they start. The demographics of our samples (refer to Table 1) also support this claim. The findings of our study also imply that CBs are in a relatively better position in meeting expectations of ITPs than OSD, and as a consequence, ITPs attached to CBs are willing to stay with the organisation more than that of ITPs attached to OSD. This again implies the importance of evaluating job expectations, experience, and met expectations of ITPs attached to different business sectors.

Finally, of the two sectors, CBs could be identified as a traditional sector where traditional careers are still feasible while OSD could be identified as a new business sector emerged from the global outsourcing context, which has created a type of jobs not existed in the country before. However, the findings of the study imply that ITPs attached to both of these sectors have concerns in fulfilling their job expectations. Firms, irrespective of the business sector, expect to leverage by attracting and retaining the most valuable people. Therefore, the findings imply the importance of understanding career issues not only in newly emerged business sectors like OSD but also in traditional business sectors like CBs.

Limitations and suggestions for further research

We have gone through a rigorous process in trying to winnow the long list of expectations and factor analysis used to derive a common set of expectations, experience, and met expectations. Future studies could use methods such as Delphi to derive the list of items to represent expectations, experience, and met expectations. Future studies could accompany survey questionnaires with in-depth interviews to assist in confirming, enriching or questioning self-reported perceptions. In this regard, future studies of longitudinal nature

could provide an in-depth understanding of this topic. When operationalizing met expectations, we used direct measures of met expectations. However, direct measures require individuals to recall their prior expectations after having been on the job for some time. With regard to data analysis, we used factors analysis as a form of data reduction and we labelled the clusters derived from factor analysis to provide readers with some sense of derived clusters for expectations. With regard to the respondents, they have voluntarily responded to the survey and their responses were anonymous. Therefore, we were unable to compare the characteristics of respondents and non-respondents.

Further, we have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated job expectations of ITPs in the South Asia. Therefore, as stated earlier, the objective of our study was to establish whether there are any differences in job expectations, experience, and met expectations of ITPs in OSD and CBs in Sri Lanka. As discussed above, we have identified significant differences in certain aspects. We believe that the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research to investigate causes for differences in job expectations, experience, and met expectations of ITPs in OSD and CBs. Future research studies could complement survey questionnaire with interviews and secondary data to provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey. Furthermore, future research could investigate whether ITPs leave both IT sector and commercial banking sector to be self-employed as their job expectations were not met sufficiently by these two business sectors.

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Tables

Table 1: Demographics of the samples

ITPs from OSD (N=342)		ITPs from CBs (N=208)	
Gender:		Gender:	
Male	74%	Male	78%
Female	26%	Female	21%
Marital status:		Marital status:	
Single	54%	Single	31%
Married	46%	Married	69%
Age:		Age:	
Mean	30 yrs	Mean	32 yrs
S.D.	3.8	S.D.	5.81
Tenure in the present workplace:		Tenure in the present workplace:	
Mean	4 yrs	Mean	8 yrs
S.D.	2.7	S.D.	5.31
Tenure in the job position:		Tenure in the job position:	
Mean	3.5yrs	Mean	3 yrs
S.D.	1.7	S.D.	0.91
Highest level of education:		Highest level of education:	
Diploma	23%	Diploma	30%
Degree	78%	Degree	70%
Total employees in the unit:		Total employees in the unit:	
Below 20	80%	Below 20	45%
More than 20	20%	More than 20	55%
Total employees in the present workplace:		Total employees in the present workplace:	
Below 300	57%	Below 300	38%
More than 300	43%	More than 300	62%

Table 2: Detailed analysis of prior work experience of respondents (N=215)

	Prior work experience %, (Mean tenure in years; S.D.)
Present workplace - OSD (N=153):	
Prior work experience in some other OSD	74, (4; 2.47)
Prior work experience in a commercial bank	3, (3.17; 1.43)
Prior work experience in a firm other than an OSD or a commercial bank	23, (2.86; 2.26)
Present workplace - CBs (N=62):	
Prior work experience in an OSD	32, (5.67; 4.3)
Prior work experience in some other commercial bank	16, (3.6; 2.40)
Prior work experience in a firm other than an OSD or a commercial bank	46, (3; 2.49)
Prior work experience both in some other commercial bank and an OSD	5, (5; 1.04)

Table 3: Summary of results- paired sample t-tests

	OSD				CBs			
	Mean	S.D.	Expectations Vs. Experience [†]	Expectations Vs. Met expectations [†]	Mean	S.D.	Expectations Vs. Experience [†]	Expectation Vs. Met expectations [†]
			<i>t</i>	<i>t</i>			<i>t</i>	<i>t</i>
Work-life balance:								
- Expectations	3.75	.66	4.184***	9.224***	4.20	.38	9.007***	22.888***
- Experience	3.45	.61			3.66	.52		
- Met expectations	2.59	.58			3.30	.48		
Identification with the organisation:			4.231***	10.952***	4.06	.43	6.948***	19.407***
- Expectations	3.71	.61			3.76	.40		
- Experience	3.51	.63			3.34	.40		
- Met expectations	2.83	.44						
Job security, remuneration and advancement opportunity:			5.024***	8.524***	4.25	.53	9.423***	18.675***
- Expectations	3.69	.65			3.73	.45		
- Experience	3.31	.44			3.29	.49		
- Met expectations	2.64	.62						
Perceptibility of expertise:			ND	15.631***	3.95	.45	ND	18.035***
- Expectations	3.80	.53			3.95	.45		
- Experience	3.80	.53			3.16	.42		
- Met expectations	2.70	.43						
Control over work:			3.583***	12.589***	3.96	.42	10.855***	21.728***
- Expectations	3.83	.54			3.48	.45		
- Experience	3.64	.49			3.38	.33		
- Met expectations	2.87	.37						
Job challenges:			6.722***	15.206***	4.00	.40	11.049***	22.130***
- Expectations	3.93	.56			3.51	.44		
- Experience	3.60	.48			3.24	.39		
- Met expectations	2.74	.39						

Note: * p<0.05; **p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

ND= no difference

[†] Analyses were done separately for each pair. To reduce the number of tables, results were shown in one table.

Table 4: Summary of results- independent sample t-tests - differences in job expectations, experience, and met expectations by sector

	Job expectations [†]	Job experience [†]	Met expectations [†]
	OSD Vs. CBs	OSD Vs. CBs	OSD Vs. CBs
	<i>t</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>t</i>
Work-life balance	-6.532***	-2.863**	-3.121**
Identification with the organisation	-5.128***	-3.714***	-1.988*
Job security, remuneration and advancement opportunity	-7.252***	-7.270***	-2.105*
Perceptibility of expertise	-2.352*	-2.352*	-2.584**
Control over work	-2.141*	2.640**	-5.648***
Job challenges	-1.095	1.481	-2.983**

Note: * p<0.05; **p<0.01, *** p<0.001

[†] Analyses were done separately for job expectations, experience, and met expectations. To reduce the number of tables, results were shown in one table. Refer to Table 3 for mean values and standard deviations.

Table 5: Summary of results - logistic regression – job expectations, experience, and met expectations by sector

	Job expectations [†]				Job experience [†]				Met expectations [†]			
	B	S.E.	Wald	Exp(B)	B	S.E.	Wald	Exp(B)	B	S.E.	Wald	Exp(B)
Age	-.010	.096	.011	.990	.051	.105	.234	1.052	-.071	.090	.610	.932
Gender	-.176	.645	.075	.838	-.080	.630	.016	.923	-.340	.535	.403	.712
Marital status	-.040	.693	.003	.961	.378	.657	.331	1.460	.895	.603	2.202	2.448
Education	.800	.594	1.810	1.225	.184	.556	.110	1.202	.604	.517	1.365	1.829
Tenure - position	-.432	.297	1.302	.239	1.182*	.288	3.859	.307	-1.232*	.252	3.842	.292
Employees - unit	2.167*	.612	12.546	8.728	1.314*	.550	5.708	3.722	1.404*	.499	7.913	4.072
Tenure – total	.594	.167	2.703	1.812	.484*	.171	8.003	1.623	.628*	.136	1.844	1.630
Employees – total	.561	.790	1.883	.993	.322	.721	1.106	1.989	.322	.291	1.293	1.576
Content plateau	.642	.057	.983	.879	.770	.213	1.323	1.491	.734	.231	1.562	.839
Hierarchical plateau	-.133	.586	1.181	1.463	-.478	.147	.969	.969	-.397	.216	.549	.781
Supervisor support	.419	.691	.847	.920	.841	.683	1.366	1.879	.711	.578	1.884	.976
Work-life balance	3.061**	.881	12.074	21.350	1.357*	.685	3.929	3.886	2.057*	.865	5.664	5.128
Identification with the organisation	2.840**	1.191	5.691	17.116	3.098***	.712	18.910	22.148	.489*	.148	1.844	1.630
Job security, remuneration and advancement opportunity	2.488**	.753	10.905	12.038	1.855**	.665	7.775	6.394	1.081*	.488	2.728	1.085
Perceptibility of expertise	2.121*	.946	5.025	.288	.351*	.569	.379	.620	.726*	.783	.860	1.484
Control over work	1.244*	1.003	1.536	.120	-.853*	.868	10.812	1.158	2.269**	.704	10.391	9.674
Job challenges	2.774	1.069	6.733	.062	-.620	.935	3.003	.198	1.326*	.679	3.817	3.265
Constant	6.281	5.305	9.419	.000	5.977	4.832	10.932	.000	2.898	3.359	.744	18.141

Note: * p<0.05; **p<0.01, *** p<0.001

[†] Analyses were done separately for job expectations, experience, and met expectations. To reduce the number of tables, results were shown in one table.

Table 6: Summary – results of hypotheses testing

Hypothesis	Result
H1	Partially supported (Table 3)
H2	Supported (Table 3)
H3	Partially supported (Table 3)
H4	Supported (Table 3)
H5	Partially supported (Table 3, 4, and 5)
H6	Partially supported (Table 3, 4, and 5)
H7	Supported (Table 3, 4, and 5)

Appendix

Appendix 1: Summary of factor analysis - expectations[†]

	F1 Work-life balance	F2 Identification with the organisation	F3 Job security, remuneration and advancement opportunity	F4 Perceptibility of expertise	F5 Control over work	F6 Job challenges
Provides sufficient leisure time to relax and be myself	.842					
Permits a balance between work and other areas of my life	.831					
Allows to put work in its place as an important, but not the only part of my life	.705					
Permits to be identified closely with the organisation		.809				
Provides status of being a part of the organisation		.850				
Provides prestige and recognition of being part of the organisation		.738				
Permits opportunities for advancement			.775			
Has an opportunity to be entitled for a good remuneration package			.886			
Provides job security			.875			
My expertise is respected by other people				.722		
Receives attention and appreciation for the work performed				.704		
I am respected for specialist skills that I bring				.824		
Increases my self-worth				.700		
Permits working independently					.742	
Allows to get the job done well through managing the efforts of others					.758	
Provides opportunity to demonstrate job responsibility					.707	
Permits to develop own methods of doing work					.730	
Provides chances to be creative and innovative						.796
Provides opportunities to lead a team on important organisational projects						.745
Gives challenges which stretch me intellectually						.743
Requires working on problems of central importance to the organisation						.793
Explained variation	36.34	11.61	8.62	6.05	5.10	4.73
Eigenvalue	8.68	3.81	2.27	2.07	1.99	1.85
Cronbach's alpha	.805	.807	.802	.741	.768	.749
Mean	3.97	3.89	3.97	3.87	3.87	3.97
Standard deviation	.59	.56	.66	.50	.50	.49

Note: Total item alpha = .927 (21 items). [†] Scale ranged from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important)

Appendix 2: Summary of factor analysis - experience[†]

	F1 Identification with the organisation	F2 Job security, remuneration and advancement opportunity	F3 Work-life balance	F4 Control over work	F5 Perceptibility of expertise	F6 Job challenges
Permits to be identified closely with the organisation	.754					
Provides status of being a part of the organisation	.821					
Provides prestige and recognition of being part of the organisation	.717					
Permits opportunities for advancement		.762				
Has an opportunity to be entitled for a good remuneration package		.739				
Provides job security		.738				
Provides sufficient leisure time to relax and be myself			.823			
Permits a balance between work and other areas of my life			.803			
Allows to put work in its place as an important, but not the only part of my life			.752			
Permits working independently				.774		
Allows to get the job done well through managing the efforts of others				.755		
Provides opportunity to demonstrate job responsibility				.761		
Permits to develop own methods of doing work				.664		
My expertise is respected by other people					.737	
Receives attention and appreciation for the work performed					.774	
I am respected for specialist skills that I bring					.795	
Increases my self-worth					.794	
Provides chances to be creative and innovative						.751
Provides opportunities to lead a team on important organisational projects						.708
Gives challenges which stretch me intellectually						.713
Requires working on problems of central importance to the organisation						.779
Explained variation	29.34	9.46	7.68	6.53	6.05	5.03
Eigenvalue	6.16	1.99	1.61	1.37	1.27	1.06
Cronbach's alpha	.743	.711	.738	.706	.752	.727
Mean	3.56	3.64	3.52	3.87	3.57	3.56
Standard deviation	.58	.55	.50	.50	.48	.47

Note: Total item alpha = .869 (21 items). [†] Scale ranged from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree)

Appendix 3: Summary of factor analysis - met expectations[†]

	F1 Control over work	F2 Work-life balance	F3 Job challenges	F4 Perceptibility of expertise	F5 Job security, remuneration and advancement opportunity	F6 Identification with the organisation
Permits working independently	.770					
Allows to get the job done well through managing the efforts of others	.753					
Provides opportunity to demonstrate job responsibility	.765					
Permits to develop own methods of doing work	.715					
Provides sufficient leisure time to relax and be myself		.730				
Permits a balance between work and other areas of my life		.742				
Allows to put work in its place as an important, but not the only part of my life		.792				
Provides chances to be creative and innovative			.733			
Provides opportunities to lead a team on important organisational projects			.714			
Gives challenges which stretch me intellectually			.797			
Requires working on problems of central importance to the organisation			.731			
My expertise is respected by other people				.714		
Receives attention and appreciation for the work performed				.763		
I am respected for specialist skills that I bring				.774		
Increases my self-worth				.742		
Permits opportunities for advancement					.788	
Has an opportunity to be entitled for a good remuneration package					.823	
Provides job security					.741	
Permits to be identified closely with the organisation						.764
Provides status of being a part of the organisation						.799
Provides prestige and recognition of being part of the organisation						.760
Explained variation	21.19	11.73	8.56	6.94	6.16	5.72
Eigenvalue	4.45	2.80	1.98	1.49	1.20	1.15
Cronbach's alpha	.723	.701	.721	.718	.713	.742
Mean	2.70	2.78	2.72	2.63	2.75	2.67
Standard deviation	.55	.43	.57	.43	.38	.40

Note: Total item alpha = .804 (21 items). [†] Scale ranged from 1 (much less than what had expected), 2 (somewhat less), 3 (about the same), 4 (somewhat more), and 5 (much more).

Appendix 4: Summary of factor analysis – hierarchical plateau, job content plateau, and perceived supervisor support

Hierarchical plateau:

I am not likely to obtain a much higher job title in my present workplace	.761
I expect to advance to a higher level in my present workplace in the near future	.783
My opportunities for upward movement are limited in my present workplace	.678
I expect to be promoted frequently in my present workplace in the future	.820
I have reached a point where I do not expect to move much higher in my present workplace	.683
The likelihood that I will get ahead in my present workplace is limited	.758
Explained variation	56.065
Eigenvalue	3.364
Cronbach's alpha	.840
Mean	2.90
Standard deviation	.67

Job content plateau:

I expect to be constantly challenged in my job	.716
I have an opportunity to learn and grow a lot in my current job	.595
My job tasks and activities have become routine for me	.634
My job responsibilities have increased significantly	.587
My job requires me to continually extent my abilities and knowledge	.727
I am challenged by my job	.710
Explained variation	40.028
Eigenvalue	2.402
Cronbach's alpha	.693
Mean	2.65
Standard deviation	.54

Perceived supervisor support:

My supervisor strongly considers my goals and values	.791
My supervisor is willing to extend itself in order to help me perform my job to the best of my ability	.824
My supervisor tries to make my job as interesting as possible	.796
Explained variation	81.57
Eigenvalue	1.63
Cronbach's alpha	.773
Mean	3.65
Standard deviation	.67
